

ILLUMINATE: A LOCALIZED TVL-EIM WEBSITE TO IMPROVE THE PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 12 PRUDENCE IN INSTALLING ELECTRICAL LIGHTING SYSTEMS ON AUXILIARY OUTLETS AND LIGHTING FIXTURES

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ABSTRACT

This action research aimed to enhance the proficiency of G12 Prudence in installing electrical lighting systems on auxiliary outlets and fixtures, ultimately leading to a competent rating in the NC II institutional assessment. It focused on implementing a localized website tailored to the specific needs of electrical students, providing a more targeted and effective learning experience in these crucial skill areas. The study assessed the performance levels of low-performing G12 students through observations and interviews, aiming to identify factors influencing their performance in installing lighting systems. This information guided the development of targeted interventions to address their specific challenges, promoting more inclusive and equitable educational outcomes. Utilizing tools like the localized website, modified rubrics, and interviews, the research demonstrated the significant impact of 'ILLUMINATE,' a localized TVL EIM Website, on improving the performance of G12 Prudence in installing lighting systems. The results highlighted a substantial difference in students' performance scores before and after the intervention, affirming the effectiveness of the localized website in enhancing learning outcomes. Based on these conclusive findings, educational institutions are strongly encouraged to integrate technology-enhanced, localized learning platforms like 'ILLUMINATE' into their curriculum for electrical technology students. This approach not only leads to substantial improvements in institutional assessments but also underscores the potential for transformative impacts on teaching methods and student achievements. This research highlights the importance of ongoing investment in tailored digital resources to optimize the educational experience for students in the field of electrical technology.

Keywords: *localized website; installing lighting system; institutional assessment; performance level; contextualized*

INTRODUCTION

Practical assessment is vital for applying theory, honing critical thinking, and enhancing overall performance. It encompasses various forms like lab reports, performance measures, and exams. It fosters practical skills, real-world application, and deeper learning. Yet, challenges like concept mastery and precise skill execution exist. These can impact performance, causing anxiety and resource constraints. A recent study published by Rahman et al. (2021) aimed to explore how practical skills influence students' academic performance by collecting real-world data. The study found that practical skills significantly impact academic performance, and students with better practical skills tend to perform better academically. The study also found that practical skills are essential for students to succeed in the workforce.

According to a recent study by HJ Walberg in 2010, several factors can impact learner performance. The research underscores that slower concept acquisition, limited retention, and uncertain practical execution accuracy are vital factors. These factors hinder efficient learning, making it challenging for students to grasp and retain new concepts. Additionally, uncertainty in reasonable execution accuracy can erode confidence and proficiency in application.

This struggle may impact overall academic performance and achievement. The G12 Prudence at Madrid National High School confronted a significant challenge related to their practical skills, resulting in consistently lower ratings during institutional assessments. Detailed observation revealed instances where students failed to install lighting systems on lighting fixtures and auxiliary outlets. Among these students, 14 needed help to meet the learning expectations. Of this group, 10 demonstrated a slower pace of concept acquisition, limited retention capacity, and uncertainty regarding the accuracy of their practical execution. These factors collectively contributed to their receiving inadequate ratings during the institutional assessment process.

The slower pace of concept acquisition, limited retention capacity, and uncertainty regarding the accuracy of practical execution can profoundly affect students' lives. These factors can lead to difficulty in keeping up with the pace of the curriculum, struggle to retain information and apply it to real-world situations, inability to perform well in practical exams and assessments, low self-esteem and confidence due to poor academic performance, anxiety and stress related to academic performance, and difficulty in pursuing higher education or career opportunities due to inadequate skills and knowledge (OECD 2020). These challenges are alarming to parents, teachers, and schools, as they can hinder students' overall development and prospects. It is essential to address these challenges by providing students with adequate support, resources, and guidance to improve their academic performance and practical skills.

The Department of Education (DepEd) mandates mastering concepts and skills as part of its mission, vision, goals, and objectives. Acquiring content knowledge and developing pedagogy is essential in realizing the DepEd's purpose of providing quality education to every Filipino. The mastery of 21st-century skills, such as critical thinking and problem-solving, is also emphasized in the preparation of educators. The Senior High School curriculum further highlights the importance of concept and skill mastery, which aims to prepare students for higher education, entrepreneurship, or employment. The senior high curriculum is designed to provide students with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies to succeed in their chosen career paths. Mastering concepts and skills is crucial in ensuring students have the competencies required to succeed in their future endeavors.

Embracing contextualization and a constructivist approach, a localized educational website with bite-sized learning activities, custom lecture demos, and offline apps can improve the performance of low-performing Grade-12 Prudence at Madrid National High School. This innovative intervention is designed to enhance their skills in installing electrical lighting systems on auxiliary outlets and lighting fixtures, offering accessible and tailored resources for better understanding and practical application, thereby improving their overall performance in this essential skill area and passing the institutional assessment in TVL – Electrical Installation and Maintenance NCII.

Research Questions

This study was intended to improve the performance of the Grade-12 Prudence of Madrid National High School in TVL-EIM by applying the ILLUMINATE – Localized TVL EIM Website. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance of G-12 Prudence in installing lighting systems on lighting fixtures and auxiliary outlets before the intervention?
2. What factors affect the student's performance in installing lighting systems on lighting fixtures and auxiliary outlets?
3. What is the performance of identified students after using the ILLUMINATE – Localized TVL EIM Website as an intervention?
4. Is there a significant difference between the performances of the identified students before and after the intervention in installing lighting systems on lighting fixtures and auxiliary outlets?

Hypothesis

At 0.05 level, it is hypothesized that:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the performances of the identified students before and after the intervention in installing lighting systems on lighting fixtures and auxiliary outlets

METHODOLOGY

The participants of this study were the Grade-12 students in TVL – EIM of Madrid National High School who were enrolled in the school year 2022-2023. There were 45 males and three females, with 48 students under Grade 12- Prudence. The intervention was catered only to the identified low-performing students. Among these students, 14 were not able to meet the expectations. Parents and other concerned stakeholders were also involved as sources of information regarding the Grade-12 learners' mastery of competency.

This action research employed a descriptive method. Furthermore, the researcher used a purposive sampling technique, also known as selective sampling, to select the study subjects. Data collection included assessing student performance using a performance-based rubric adapted from TESDA Training Regulations. Adjectival rating will adhere to DepEd Order No.8, s. 2015. Interviews were conducted with learners who did not meet the learning expectations in formative assessments and parents and other stakeholders who influenced the learners' performance. Data consolidation utilized Frequency Count, Percentage Count, and Paired Sample T-test analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1. The performance of G-12 Prudence in installing electrical lighting systems on auxiliary outlets and lighting fixtures before the intervention.

Numerical Rating	Adjectival Rating	Frequency (Number of Learners)
90 and above	Outstanding	12
85-89	Very Satisfactory	14
80-84	Satisfactory	7
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	1
74 and below	Did not meet Expectations	14
Total		48

Table 2. Factors affecting the learners' performances in installing electrical lighting systems in auxiliary outlets and lighting fixtures.

Factors	Number of Learners
Difficulty in grasping concepts, retaining information, and uncertain practical execution.	10
Misinterpretation of Instructions	1
Distractions or Lack of Focus	1
Time Management Issues	2
Total	14

Table 3. Performance of identified students after using ILLUMINATE – Localized TVL EIM Website as an intervention.

Student	Before the Utilization of an Intervention		After the Utilization of an Intervention	
	Scores	Adjectival Rating	Scores	Adjectival Rating
1	72	Did not meet expectations	90	Outstanding
2	60	Did not meet expectations	88	Very Satisfactory
3	50	Did not meet expectations	84	Satisfactory
4	54	Did not meet expectations	84	Satisfactory
5	66	Did not meet expectations	88	Very Satisfactory
6	72	Did not meet expectations	92	Outstanding
7	60	Did not meet expectations	88	Very Satisfactory
8	60	Did not meet expectations	88	Very Satisfactory
9	54	Did not meet expectations	84	Satisfactory
10	54	Did not meet expectations	84	Satisfactory

Table 4. The significant difference between the performances of the identified students before and after the intervention in installing electrical lighting systems on auxiliary outlets and lighting fixtures.

Intervention	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Before	60.200	7.685	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis	There is a significant difference
After	87.000	2.867			

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the performance of G-12 Prudence in installing lighting systems on lighting fixtures and auxiliary outlets before the intervention. Out of 48 students, 70.83% or 34 learners got a passing performance rate, while 29.17% did not meet the expectation and failed. This implies that only some students need scaffolding, specifically installing lighting systems on lighting fixtures and auxiliary outlets. There could be factors behind their unsatisfactory performance that need immediate aid.

Table 2 outlines the factors contributing to unsatisfactory performance in installing electrical lighting systems on auxiliary outlets and fixtures. Most low-performing learners needed help grasping concepts, retaining information, and uncertain practical execution. This indicates that these learners need further guidance and facilitative learning resources to improve retention and application of skills. In consonance with the study published by HJ Walberg in 2010, it highlighted that slower concept grasp, limited retention, and uncertain practical execution are significant factors. These factors impede effective learning, making it challenging for students to understand and remember new concepts. Moreover, uncertainty in practical execution can diminish confidence and proficiency in application.

Table 3 depicts identified students' performance after using the ILLUMINATE – Localized TVL EIM Website as an intervention. The outcomes indicate a notable improvement in student performance following their involvement with the ILLUMINATE intervention. Specifically, two students received an Outstanding rating, 4 achieved a Very Satisfactory rating, and another 4 attained a Satisfactory rating. This underscores the intervention's effectiveness in promoting concept acquisition, information retention, and skill execution accuracy. It reinforces the importance of accessible learning resources, contextualized content, and a ubiquitous approach to nurturing skills in a specific discipline. Backed by Ballesteros' (2015) study on the application of localization and contextualization in science education found that utilizing localized and context-specific teaching resources can enhance students' comprehension of scientific concepts.

Table 4 reveals the significant difference between the performances of the identified students before and after the intervention in installing electrical lighting systems on auxiliary outlets and lighting fixtures. As the outcome depicts, the mean scores of the students after the intervention, which is 87.000, were significantly higher compared to their mean scores before the intervention, which was 60.200. This indicates that there's an improvement in their performances in installing lighting systems on lighting fixtures and auxiliary outlets after engaging in the intervention.

Additionally, it can be observed from the table that the standard deviation after the intervention was lesser, which means their scores are closely clustered to the mean; thus, their scores are not widely spread from each other, and all of them were influenced and aided by ILLUMINATE as an intervention. On top of that, it can be gleaned from the table that the computed p-value is less than the critical value at the 0.05 level, which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that the student's scores differ significantly before and after the intervention. Further, the result could mean that the ILLUMINATE – Localized TVL EIM Website as an intervention is effective and efficient in developing students' concept acquisition, information retention, and skills accuracy. Its features, like the bite-sized learning activity sheets, localized lecture-demonstration videos, and offline mobile apps, helped them master the competency. This conclusion supports the finding of Brown (2020), which highlighted the role of localized websites in exposing students to authentic language use, enriching the language learning experience, and promoting a deeper understanding of concepts. The above findings also relate to Perin's (2011) study, which investigated how contextualization can enhance academic outcomes for underprepared students. The research revealed that contextualization aids in fostering a deeper grasp of the subject matter and improves student performance. Furthermore, customized demonstration videos and locally adapted resources can complement in-class teaching, offering students extra learning possibilities.

Conclusions

The study's findings indicate that targeted intervention was crucial for G-12 Prudence students in installing lighting systems. Factors contributing to their unsatisfactory performance were identified, aligning with HJ Walberg's research. Following the ILLUMINATE intervention, significant improvements were observed, supported by Ballesteros' study on localization and contextualization. Table 4 shows a substantial increase in post-intervention scores, affirming the effectiveness of ILLUMINATE. The reduced standard deviation and significant p-value underscore the intervention's positive impact. Overall, this research emphasizes the importance of tailored digital resources in enhancing learning outcomes for students in electrical technology, aligning with Brown and Perin's findings.

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions, it is recommended to implement the ILLUMINATE – Localized TVL EIM Website as a standard intervention for senior high school students in electrical technology programs. This tailored digital resource effectively improves concept acquisition, retention, and skills execution. Additionally, it promotes a more consistent performance among students. The integration of such localized, technology-enhanced platforms should be encouraged across educational institutions to optimize learning outcomes in the field of electrical technology.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to rigorous ethical standards throughout its execution. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose and their voluntary participation. Respondents were assured of their absolute freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without any repercussions. Anonymity was strictly maintained to safeguard

the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents. They were not subjected to any form of harm, be it physical, psychological, or otherwise, throughout the study.

Moreover, there was a meticulous effort to avoid any conflict of interest in the conduct of this research. Plagiarism was vehemently avoided, and proper citation and attribution were consistently observed. The interpretation of the findings was approached with impartiality and objectivity, ensuring no bias in the analysis or reporting of results. It is imperative to emphasize that the results of this study are intended solely for research purposes and will not be used for any other intent or agenda.

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